

DEFINITION AND MANUFACTURING OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED ALUMINUM FOR EMBEDDED ELECTRONIC PACKAGINGS

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ABSTRACT

A numerical analysis of the temperatures distribution in a generalized case of a component dissipating heat in a few millimeters thick plate was led. Continuous pitch-based carbon fibers, C_f , is a viable solution as an alternative to the current use of aluminum. The numerical simulation helped determining the specifications of the material according to different combinations of thermal conductivities along the three main axes in order to compete aluminum. A bibliographic review of liquid and solid processing routes for this composite material is investigated.

1 INTRODUCTION

Weight savings in aerospace industry is one of the most crucial challenges it has to cope with. In the past decades, the size and weight of electronic components have decreased significantly. Meanwhile, the contribution of packaging to embedded electronic systems' weight has increased. The main function of these packagings – currently made of aluminum – is to enable sufficient heat dissipation in order to keep components under their maximum service temperature. The objective is to develop new materials to reduce the weight of the packaging. One solution would be to develop polymer matrix composites, which use is being widely generalized in aircrafts for their good mechanical properties. However, these materials are confronted to limitations when it comes to fulfil thermal functions despite the development of pitch-based carbon fibers which show a high thermal conductivity because of their high graphitization level and specific structure [1,2].

Combining good thermal properties of aluminum with highly conductive carbon fibers has been identified to be a good way to cope with that double challenge [3]: reducing the system weight while keeping efficient heat sink.

The work presented here is mostly based on a numerical analysis of the temperatures distribution in a generalized case of a component dissipating heat in a few millimeters thick plate. These numerical simulations helped determining the specifications of the material according to different combinations of thermal conductivities along the three axes to compete aluminum.

Those results led us to be able to select some processing routes among many in order to elaborate the aluminum matrix composite.

2 NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

Finite Elements method were used through Abaqus to give an overview of the potential efficiency of a pitch based carbon fiber reinforced aluminum composite to fulfill the requirements of an industrial embedded electronic packaging.

After validation of the numerical model, analysis were run to investigate the role of each thermal conductivity main component – k_x , k_y and k_z – on the maximum temperature reached by the electronic component surface. The influence of plate thickness is also investigated in sight of mass reduction.

2.1 Analysis model

The model used in this work consists in a $250 \times 80 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$ plate in contact with a centered electronic component. Both share a $40 \times 40 \text{ mm}^2$ contact area. The study is strictly stationary. The thermal solicitations are defined according to an industrial packaging (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Description of thermal solicitations on the plate.

On Figure 1, the numbers 1, 2, 3 and 4 correspond to four different thermal conditions :

1. Transfer due to the main component directly in contact with the plate is defined by a 6000 W/m^2 heat flux;
2. Convective transfer from the plate to the air defined by $h_{\text{top}} = 50 \text{ W/(m}^2\text{K)}$ and $T_{\text{exch}} = 59^\circ\text{C}$;
3. Conductive transfer due to secondary components defined by a uniformly distributed 200 W/m^2 flux;
4. Transfer to the side built in contact with the plate with a 4 K/W contact resistance. This transfer is hereby represented by a mathematically equivalent convective transfer defined by $h_{\text{side}} = 1000 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$) and $T_{\text{exchSide}} = 70^\circ\text{C}$.

Because of the symmetries, numerical simulations were lead on a quarter of the plate as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 : 3-D upper (left) and lower (right) representations of a quarter of the studied plate.

This analysis gives access to the contact temperature T_{max} between the packaging (the plate) and the most dissipative electronic component of the equipment. The influence of k_x , k_y and k_z on this result has been investigated in the simple cases of isotropic or orthotropic materials.

2.2 Studied materials

For this analysis, four simple kinds of materials were considered (Table 1) :

- Isotropic : $k = k_x = k_y = k_z$; $k_{ij, i \neq j} = 0$ ($i, j = x, y, z$)
- Orthotropic XY : $k_{xy} = k_x = k_y > k_z$; $k_{ij, i \neq j} = 0$
- Orthotropic unidirectional (UD) in direction X : $k_x \geq k_y$; $k_{ij, i \neq j} = 0$
- Orthotropic unidirectional (UD) in direction Y : $k_y \geq k_x$; $k_{ij, i \neq j} = 0$

The reference material (noted ref in Table 1) that will be used to compare results to existing device is an isotropic material with $k = 140 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$.

Maximum conductivities for UD X and UD Y materials have been selected according to the results obtained by Ueno et al. [4,5] for a unidirectional pitch based carbon fiber reinforced aluminum

composite.

Maximum conductivity for orthotropic XY material was taken considering that the rule of mixtures cannot lead to a higher in-plane conductivity than half of the maximum conductivity of UD.

Maximum orthotropic conductivity considered in this work is close to pure aluminum conductivity, considering that no other monolithic material with higher conductivity can lead to lower the weight of the plate (beryllium was not considered due to its high cost).

<i>Material</i>	<i>Variable components</i>		<i>Fixed components</i>
Isotropic XYZ	k	100 - 140 (ref) - 200	
Orthotropic XY	k_{xy}	100 - 200 - 300	$k_z = 30$
Orthotropic UD X	k_x	100 - 200 - 300 - 400 - 600	$k_y = 100 ; k_z = 30$
Orthotropic UD Y	k_y	100 - 200 - 300 - 400 - 600	$k_x = 100 ; k_z = 30$

Table 1 : Definition of the materials used for the analysis, all conductivity values in $Wm^{-1}K^{-1}$

2.3 Influence of thermal conductivity components on T_{max}

Results of the simulations for all four types of materials are presented on Figure 3. It confirms the low influence of k_z on T_{max} . If we compare T_{max} for an isotropic material – $k = 200 Wm^{-1}K^{-1}$ and Orthotropic XY material – $k_{xy} = 200 Wm^{-1}K^{-1} ; k_z = 30 Wm^{-1}K^{-1}$, the difference of T_{max} is only 0.1°C. In our case, the plate thickness is too low to give z component a significant influence on T_{max} .

Figure 3 : Evolution of T_{max} with the variation of the variable component for the different types of material (Table 1).

However, we can see that the orientation of the reinforcement is of a major importance. While a UD X material with $k_x = 600 Wm^{-1}K^{-1}$ barely reduces T_{max} by 0.14°C compared to $T_{max,ref}$, it is already lowered by 0.67°C for UD Y – $k_y = 200 Wm^{-1}K^{-1}$. A closer look to temperature maps (Figure 4) allows explaining this difference: in the UD Y case, the temperature is homogenized all over the plate and the difference between the highest and the lowest temperature is 4.0°C. Meanwhile, in the UD X case, this

difference is more than doubled (9.7°C). In this case, the side thermal resistance is too high to enable sufficient heat dissipation and the temperature rises above the electronic component. In the other case (UD Y), enhancing k_y enables an efficient and more homogeneous heat dissipation by convection on the top of the plate.

Figure 4 : Temperature maps for UDX – $k_x = 600 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ (left) and UDY – $k_y = 600 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ (right).

Within the bounds fixed, orthotropic XY material leads to enhanced performance but not as much as UD Y solution. However, optimization of k_y/k_x ratio would provide more complete information.

2.4 Influence of plate thickness on T_{\max}

In order to decrease the plate weight, a decrease in the plate thickness is the most interesting option. Indeed the high graphitization of pitch based C_f give a density – around 2.2 g/cm^3 . Then Al- $C_{f,\text{pitch}}$ composite would not lead itself to a significant decrease in material density compared to aluminum. Still, increasing the material conductivity enables to decrease the plate thickness while keeping on coping with thermal issue.

Figure 5 : Temperature maps for UDY – $k_y = 600$, $k_x = 100$, $k_z = 30$ – for thickness e between 1 and 2 mm

For each type of materials defined previously, plate thickness was tested between 2mm (reference plate) and 1 mm. Results for UDY material show that T_{max} increases with the reduction of the plate thickness as expected (Figure 5). However, the lower temperature along the free edge of the plate is not much affected by variations of the plate thickness. This evolution has been seen on every tested configuration.

In all configurations we can observe that the evolution of T_{max} with the plate thickness is almost linear with the thickness inverse for any conductivity configuration (Figure 6). However, the slope is not the same for each. Isotropic and UD X materials are clearly more sensitive to thickness variations whereas UD Y is the less sensitive it could enable to divide the thickness by two and still enhance performance compared to the reference case.

Figure 6 : Evolution of T_{max} with plate thickness for four kind of materials

2.5 Conclusion on numerical analysis

This preliminary work on a general case inspired by an industrial device comforts the idea that $Al-C_{f,pitch}$ composite is a viable solution to enhance thermal dissipation and decrease the mass of the current packaging.

Developing a unidirectional composite with great conductivity along the length of the plate (UD Y) leads to greatly reduce the contact temperature by enabling more homogeneous heat evacuation through convection to the external atmosphere. Furthermore, we have seen that the higher k_y , the less influence has the thickness of the plate on the maximum temperature.

Now the viability of such a material has been shown, the question of processing can be set. Two different routes are under investigation: liquid and solid processing.

3 ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITE PROCESSING

Aluminum is a light material with a low fusion temperature and good castability. Hence, liquid processing seems an easy way to produce the desired composite. However, this route has to cope with carbon-aluminum system's wetting and reactivity issues. Therefore, powder metallurgy can stand as a viable option to face these problematics if no sufficient compromise can be found.

3.1 Liquid processing

Liquid aluminum on solid carbon is close to be a totally non wetting system with a wetting angle of 160° at $700^\circ C$ [6]. This poor wettability is partly due to the omnipresent alumina layer around any

aluminum droplet [7]. In addition, if this oxide layer is partially removed and “real contact” is set between Al and C, these species react to form aluminum carbides Al_4C_3 [8,9]. This carbide presence tends to depreciate the mechanical [10,11] and thermal properties [12] of the final composites.

Another problematic of such processing is micro segregation of alloying elements around fibers resulting in the same degradations of properties [13]. This problem can be avoided using non alloyed aluminum.

In order to improve wettability, different coatings have been investigated, some ceramic [14–16], some metallic [10,11,17] but none of them have led to satisfying results: ceramic coatings led to embrittlement while metallic coatings gives rise to micro segregation of intermetallic compounds along carbon fibers.

Classic processing routes such as gas pressure infiltration have been success full to process Al continuous C_f composites. However, poor wettability requires the process parameters to be well selected in order to avoid preform deformation or break. Continuous processes have been set up under pressure [18] or assisted by ultrasonic by ultrasound [19]. Unfortunately, results are often declared to suffer insufficient reproducibility [15].

Wetting has been widely improved by treating fibers with flux. These are compounds able to dissolve the alumina layer. A 50° wetting angle have been achieved with K_2ZrF_6 flux [20] and perfect wetting was achieved with $KI-K_2TiF_6$ flux [21,22]. However, chemical mechanisms involved result in increasing carbide formation. Though, these treatments have proven to be reproducible [16,20] and a compromise between carbide formation and infiltration will be investigated to obtain not perfect but sufficiently performant composite.

Meanwhile, powder metallurgy may be a good alternative to avoid these problems.

3.2 Solid processing

Powder metallurgy generally consists in holding powder under pressure and at a temperature below its fusion temperature in order to densify the solid powder via multiple diffusion phenomena.

As the aluminum would be kept in solid state, wetting issues are no more implied. Moreover, diffusion phenomena are widely slowed compared to liquid state, which means such processing would suppress Al-C reactivity as well. Aluminum reinforced by short carbon fibers composites have already been successfully obtained by powder metallurgy [23,24] after stirring fibers with powder.

Still, as we seek to produce a continuous reinforcement, another way to infiltrate fibers with the powder is to be found. The use of a binder set before hot pressing have been shown to be possible for Ti/SiC/C composite [25,26]. Still, fiber orientation is not ensured to be kept and they may get broken during pressing.

Continuous deposition of powder along fibers has been investigated as well for SiC filaments [27]. Those were then placed as desired and sintered. However, such a process would be difficult to adapt to carbon fibers geometry because of the smallest diameter of carbon filaments which furthermore are packed by thousands in a fiber.

Another way to facilitate the keep of fibers orientation is to use aluminum foils instead of powders. It has been shown that fiber swimming is way reduced using this method [28,29]. Though, the alumina layer acts as a diffusion barrier during aluminum sintering. Its rupture during the process has been shown to be the key to obtain well sintered aluminum [30,31] and foils are not inclined to achieve sufficient rupture during classic hot pressing [15].

Still, during the ten last years, the development of Spark Plasma Sintering (SPS) has proven to be an efficient technology to easily sinter numerous materials and its use will be studied for both foils and powder in our future works.

4 CONCLUSION

The weight of the embedded electronic packaging is to be decreased. A solution would be to replace aluminum by metal matrix composites. Numerical preliminary work on a general case inspired by an industrial device confirms the idea that $Al-C_{f,pitch}$ composite is a viable solution to enhance thermal dissipation and decrease the mass of the current packaging. It has led us to first conclusions about the reinforcement direction to privilege in order to achieve mass reduction.

Bibliographic review of metal matrix composite and especially Aluminum matrix composite lead to three options:

- Liquid processing with the use of a flux treatment of the fibers may lead to obtain not the best but the cheapest material under the condition that the aluminum carbide formation is controlled.
- Powder processing is a way to overpass the wetting and reactivity issues of the Al-C system. Still, achieving homogeneous distribution of filaments and the infiltration of metal among them would not be easy to achieve.
- Foil processing exhibits good fiber placement control but a more difficult sintering.

Our future works will consist in testing the practical viability of selected processing routes of the composite.

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